

Analysis of Students' Examination Post Covid-19 Results and Pre Covid-19 Results: Case Study of the International University of Management

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ABSTRACT: Within the COVID-19 move to online instruction, numerous educator teachers have looked for out video conference innovations (such as zoom) pointing to reproduce conventional classrooms online. At confront esteem, synchronous video shows up to offer more prompt replicability of existing face to face synchronous teaching. However, moving academically from one medium to another is not continuously a smooth move. The COVID-19 situation has constrained pressing moves, and without satisfactory openings to plan for a modern medium, a few teaches have struggled. Higher instruction (HE) has seen a developing drift towards online study. Be that as it may, educating is profoundly associated to one's beliefs, values, and commitments and to connections with understudies. A change in the mode of instruction and instructional method has the potential to disrupt these profound and individual associations giving rise to an emotional reaction. In later times, unsettling influences, such as pandemics, common calamities, and social distress have put colleges in unsteady circumstances, influencing instructive forms. The length of unsteady circumstances is unusual and can be weeks or a long time. In spite of these disturbances, colleges have to be proceed to satisfy their mission to teach youthful individuals. In arrange to examine the relocation to online learning beneath the COVID-19 widespread and look at understudy and workforce recognitions and lessons learned, a writing think about on flexible organizations and scholastic progression and a case study of the International University of Management.

KEY WORDS: Covid-19, Examination results, High institution, Online and Learning

BACKGROUND

Before covid-19 most Universities all over the globe were using face to face teaching approach. Lockdowns, social removing, and COVID secure cleanliness hones have rendered the regular face-to-face course conveyance alternatives all but outlandish for numerous higher instruction teach around the world Darren , Chugh & Luck (2021). A constrained move to online learning has been the as it were reasonable alternative for anticipating a discount closure of numerous teach. The entrenchment of the COVID-19 widespread within the everyday lives of billions of individuals over the world has significantly affected the way exercises are carried out including human-to-human intuitive that pre-COVID once in a while required a moment thought presently require cautious pre-planning some time recently they can be carried out. Higher instruction teach (HEIs) have too been caught up in this modern mode of social interaction. They have had to quickly adjust to an environment where conventional face-to-face (F2F) classroom situations are essentially more challenging (Bryson & Andres, 2020).

The COVID-19 widespread constrained numerous higher instruction teach over the globe to apply better approaches of instructing and testing to moderate wellbeing dangers for teaches and understudies. Particularly the expanded dependence on online exams has lighted talks about on whether this strategy of execution evaluation comes with higher dangers for scholastic judgment than on-site exams, as understudies as far as anyone knows have more openings to deceive (Bilen, & Matros, 2020; Gamage, Silva, & Gunawardhana, 2020); & Moralista, & Oducado, 2020). Whereas earlier inquire about on scholarly untrustworthiness is uncertain with respect to the address of whether online testing cultivates untrustworthy behaviour Holden, Kuhlmeier, & Norris (2020), states that the broad and sudden move from on-site to online testing within the higher instruction division within the wake of the widespread speaks to an unparalleled occasion.

Central to concerns of transitioning face to face instruction to online conveyance are the educating practises and regulatory back required to maintain important understudy engagement (Wingo et al., 2017). Such contemplations are regularly established within the teach being instructed and the characteristics of target learners. For illustration, medication and other health-related courses that

have a down to earth component would require exceptionally diverse educating approaches and learning assets to a preparing program in advanced statistical methods. In a web environment, what was once exceptionally simple to achieve face to face like common sense exhibits, gets to be very challenging requiring subject matter specialists to gotten to be capable at the utilize of quickly advancing learning advances that are not commonly utilized to instruct hands-on exercises in their field (Mitchell, 2020).

The purpose of this paper is to compare the results of post covid-19 and pre covid-19 results of first education students at University of Namibia.

Four specific research questions were identified to drive the research effort.

1. How did the educational technologies assist in the transition to online assessment?
2. What were the challenges students and staff experienced during the transition to online assessment?
3. How were the results before online transition and post online?
4. What are best practices learned through the transition?

LITERATURE

This literature reviewed the current and emerging literature on the transition to online assessment by institutions of higher learning. Professionals characterize instructive appraisal as the method of gathering data around understudy learning and has a few sorts, techniques, and approaches. Nicol (2008) contends that “assessment is said to drive understudy learning: it can give the inspiration for learning (e.g., through the granting of marks and grades), but it also empowers learning to require put through the arrangement of feedback.” It can take the shape of developmental evaluation, which takes put amid a course to help understudy learning, illuminate instructors of their instructing hones, and give criticism and feedback.

1.1 Transition to online assessment

Moving appraisal from a physical classroom environment to a web one is challenging since “often the allurements or commonly utilized approach is to reflect face-to-face techniques and practices” (Bailey et al. 2015, p.112). In any case, innovation can offer appraisal much more in terms of get to and bolster in its different stages, to be specific assignment plan, appraisal or translation, and criticism and reviewing, as Nicol (2008) explains: Virtual Learning Situations (e.g. Slate, Moodle) can make it simpler to display evaluation assignments to understudies (e.g. to distribute assignment prerequisites, the criteria to be utilized in appraisal and the timings for entries) and to track and record understudy advance (e.g. programmed time logging of exercises and task entries).

The COVID-19 widespread driven to a serious disturbance of educating all through higher instruction teach around the world (Marinoni, Van't Land, & Jensen, 2020). College teaches had to discover quick reactions and frequently moved from on-site to online educating in a matter of days (Crawford, Butler-Henderson, Rudolph, Malkawi, Glowatz, Burton, Magni, & Lam, 2020). This implied that higher instruction professionals were completely involved by setting up virtual learning situations, investigating instruments they had never utilized some time recently, and looking for ways to lock in with their understudies, which was frequently seen as a straining involvement (Daumiller, Rinas, Hein, Janke, Dickhäuser, & Dresel, 2021). With respect to testing, educates had to depend on a wide extend of neighbourhood ad-hoc arrangements frequently bound to official rules that higher instruction educate and government organizations had created beneath solid time weight. Whereas a few early adopters that as of now had involvement with online testing earlier to COVID-19 may have adapted way better with this move, it stands to reason that this connected as it were to a little minority of educate and educates (Clark, Callam, Paul, Stoltzfus, & Turner, 2020).

Data innovation (IT) instruments and other framework utilized to back higher instruction can be classified into two wide camps: no concurrent and synchronous (Larasati & Santoso, 2017; Lim, 2017). No concurrent learning frameworks are built on communication stages that don't require time-sensitive interactions between partners within the instruction handle (Larasati & Santoso, 2017). Learning Administration Frameworks (LMSs) such as Moodle and Writing board are cases of well-established remove learning stages that are organized to encourage partner intuitive based on a ‘request-response’ system unconstrained by time confinements. Learning Administration Frameworks (LMSs) such as Moodle and Slate are illustrations of well-established separate learning stages that are organized to encourage partner intuitive based on a ‘request-response’ system unconstrained by time impediments. On the other hand, synchronous online learning including the real-time compatibility of data is ordinarily

conducted through video conferencing instruments such as Zoom and Skype (Janghorban et al., 2014; Kohnke & Moorhouse, 2020). These have been significant to the endeavours of most HEIs to reproduce classroom situations online. Be that as it may, a combination of the two modes of engagement is vital to duplicate all face to face guidelines exercises in a simply online environment (McDaniels et al., 2016).

Challenges faced by students and staff during online transition

In a mixed learning circumstance, communication actually takes put in both synchronous and offbeat ways. For illustration, a question-and-answer session in a lesson instructional exercise is an illustration of real-time communication, though the posting of appraisal necessities on a college take note board could be a shape of communication that's not time-sensitive. In a web environment, it would be perfect to require advantage of both shapes of communication in course conveyance (Lowenthal et al., 2017). As detailed in Davies et al. (2020)'s research paper of organization reactions to COVID-19 at four Chinese colleges, understudies acknowledged the adaptability and believe that offbeat course conveyance gave them to oversee their ponders. An interchange see displayed by Romero-Ivanova et al. (2020)'s members in her ponder of computerized hone amid COVID-19 was that synchronous instruments such as Zoom are important in supporting a sense of connectedness in an something else disconnected circumstance. Both workforce and HEIs ought to carefully consider the capacity of ICT instruments to back both modes of communication some time recently joining them into course conveyance frameworks. This will too depend on the requests of the course substance, understudy inspiration and needs, and accessible specialized back (Watts, 2016).

The specialized issues which will stand up to understudies in online learning circumstances are subordinate on numerous components, such as the quality of communications foundation and the accessibility and get to program and equipment stages to support learning. One of the foremost fundamental impediments to transitioning to online learning specified within the considers was palatable web network (Chan & Wilson, 2020; Lassoued et al., 2020). This issue was especially predominant in farther regions of Centre East nations where web network is troublesome and gives constrained transfer and download speeds (Lassoued et al., 2020). Stage get to issues and computer program issues were moreover a concern for members in Mouchantaf (2020)'s ponder of educator viewpoints of online learning in Lebanon, and Rizun and Strzelecki (2020)'s affect investigation of online learning in Poland. There's no one-size-fits all approach that will meet the assorted needs of learners from distinctive disciplines over the globe. University organizations ought to receive adaptable approaches to innovation appropriation that completely consider the one of a kind circumstances of learners in particular areas and circumstances. The progressing challenge for college communities is to recognize and adjust unused IT advances and administrations to the administration of information and learning forms (Gros & García-Peñalvo, 2016).

Staff and understudies ought to be competent and certain in both academic and specialized perspectives of instructing and learning online. In Lassoued et al. (2020)'s think about on deterrents to online learning, the creators recognize workforce competence in online evaluation and understudy troubles in altering to online learning as noteworthy boundaries to effective e-learning move. This shortage in acing online educating and learning styles is compounded by a need of staff and student proficiency within the utilize of online advances as found within the think about on the computerized competence of staff and understudies at a Spanish college (Sales et al., 2020). This clear shortfall in advanced education may well be due to the nonattendance of regulation bolster, as proposed in Mouchantaf (2020)'s study. Directors ought to not as it were energize teachers to preserve capability in cutting edge e-learning devices, but moreover give openings to create abilities in best practice teaching and educational programs advancement for their teach (Schmidt et al., 2016). This is often typified inside the TPACK system. A Chinese research of four colleges uncovered that plagiarization was an issue of concern for English dialect evaluation in an internet environment (Davies et al., 2020). The truth that numerous understudies are mindful that replicating work without attribution is off-base does not show up to prevent numerous understudies (Sales et al., 2020). The challenge here for EAP instructors is how to convey devices such as Turnitin and PeerMark to relieve occasions of online cheating. Davies et al. (2020) propose that occasions of literary theft can be relieved by giving understudies with more compelling input on draft entries. Most of these challenges therefore are common across globe hence can be traced in the local institutions of high learning. Cheating was too cited as a issue in online exams as instructors cannot promptly confirm the personality of each examination candidate (Lassoued et al., 2020; Sahbaz, 2020). Permitting understudies to control their environment could be a challenge to evaluation genuineness. One approach to moderating endeavours to commit scholarly untruthfulness may be to utilize a suite of advances to both confirm understudies and confirm the creativity and genuineness of their work.

Best online practices learned through the transition

It was clear from the inspected literatures that organization back was imperative to the victory of transitioning to online learning (Alqahtani & Rajkhan, 2020; Davies et al., 2020; Hartshorn & McMurry, 2020; Kara et al., 2020; Tartavulea et al., 2020; Todd, 2020). The proposed back changes seem take numerous shapes such as giving clarity on plans and choices as they advance (Davies et al., 2020), giving back assets for staff and understudies battling with transitional courses of action to online learning (Hartshorn & McMurry, 2020), and paying for memberships for prevalent SM stages utilized by staff (Kara et al., 2020). It is unlikely to anticipate staff and understudies to consistently adjust to online learning spaces by rehashing designs of conduct and forms that worked in a F2F circumstance. Organization back at the exceptionally slightest ought to incorporate the provisioning of fitting back for specialized issues related to online learning, preparing for both understudies and workforce to use online learning engagement openings, and a commitment to bolster the advancement of multi-media learning materials custom-made to online situations (Kebritchi et al., 2017).

In spite of the constrained move to online learning, there was a discernible inclination apparent in numerous thinks about for a few frame of F2F instruction to be proceeded. This inclination took the shape of conventional classroom-based instruction (Garris & Bit, 2020; Mouchantaf, 2020; Rizun & Strzelecki, 2020; Tartavulea et al., 2020) and mixed learning alternatives (Al-Balas et al., 2020; Alqahtani & Rajkhan, 2020; Kaur et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020). Mixed learning can be seen as a half breed environment that combines the benefits of conventional F2F learning spaces whereas abusing online advances that improve learning substance and conveyance alternatives. A mixed learning environment may be the leading choice for educate post-COVID to use the lessons learned from the online involvement whereas holding the focal points of conventional F2F approaches. (Kaur et al., 2020).

METHODOLOGY

Numerous strategies can be utilized to develop an audit of accessible writing. One commonly acknowledged approach is to do document analysis (which were the results analysis) related to a point of intrigued as broadly and comprehensively as conceivable, capturing a wide run of results and sees on a request about address of interested. A more strong and quantifiable look strategy is the orderly survey. This sort of writing audit requires the advancement of a look convention that portrays definitions, look strings, look procedures, consideration and avoidance criteria, and an approach to integrating extricated data (Mallett et al., 2012).

RESULTS ANALYSIS

BREAKDOWN OF SUBJECT PASS RATE BY CAMPUS July 2020 post covid-19 results.

Table 1: Subject Pass rate by Campus

Campus Name	# of Subjects Written	# of Passes	Percentage
COASTAL CAMPUS	4462	4245	95
NKURENKURU CAMPUS	4700	4641	99
ONGWEDIVA CAMPUS	12029	11710	97
SWAKOPMUND CAMPUS	324	287	89
WINDHOEK CAMPUS	21251	20061	94
Grand Total	42766	40944	96

Table 1 shows the percentage of subjects written versus the pass rate by campus.

BREAKDOWN OF SUBJECT PASS RATE BY CAMPUS PRE COVID-19 RESULTS

July 2019

Table 2: Subject Pass rate by Campus

Campus Name	# of Subject	# of Passes	Percentage
NKURENKURU CAMPUS	3973	3018	76
ONGWEDIVA CAMPUS	11663	8885	76
SWAKOPMUND CAMPUS	318	161	51
WALVIS BAY CAMPUS	3928	2920	74
WINDHOEK CAMPUS	19678	14477	74
Grand Total	39560	29461	74

Table 2 shows the percentage of subject registration versus the pass rate by campus.

DISCUSSION

As shown in the tables above, table one show that the post covid-19 results were extremely high and students performed well; most campuses pass rate reached 95% to 99% pass rate which translate extremely well. On the other hand the pre covid-19 results show a drop in examination pass rate as shown in table 2. The table 2 results ranges from 50% to 74 % pass rate which shows a huge drop compared to post covid-19 results across campuses. It is conceivable that amid the COVID-19 widespread, the major changes to the instruction framework guided more prominent understudy achievements. In back, one considers appears that electronic stages utilized amid the COVID-19 widespread gave understudies an advantage over conventional learning (Pei & Wu, 2019) by moving forward their scholastic skillset (Elzainy et al., 2020). Thus, e-learning innovations utilized amid the widespread have possibly reinforced the communication channel between understudies and their teachers, coming about in higher scholastic execution (Alqahtani & Rajkhan, 2020).

Today's learner desires concerning e-learning are exceptionally diverse from those of customary learners. The COVID-19 widespread has modified the instructive needs of the segment, permitting understudies to memorize the most recent innovations (e.g., smartphones, tablets). The COVID-19 virtual instructive framework has driven understudies to think about at their ease and concurring to their possess necessities (Radha et al., 2020). The innovation appropriation within the COVID-19 widespread permitted for the creation of an intelligently medium by giving students access to broad scholarly assets such as a web library, instructional exercises, applications, and courses, hence improving their learning involvement. This can be seen on the displayed results in table 1 and table 2 above, as there are disparities in pre covid-19 and post covid-19 results at International University of management campuses. Amid the COVID-19 widespread, ICT has definitely changed the learning framework by building up an intuitively medium for understudies, upgrading their scholarly execution. Understudies who favour the virtual stage perform way better than when utilizing the ordinary way of educating. One ponder in Poland appeared that the noteworthy changes brought around by the widespread modified educating strategies. The conditions required to encourage COVID-19 lessening measures driven understudies to easily move their learning exercises from conventional in-class to virtual learning (Ożadowicz, 2020). Another ponder appears that this effective move has given understudies with favourable learning conditions, hence making strides their scholarly execution (Gelles et al., 2020).

In any case, innovation may be a crucial figure in supporting the understudy learning handle. The COVID-19 episode has quickened the online learning framework by giving favourable working conditions to understudies (Gelles et al., 2020). The effective usage of an e-learning framework generally depends on the students' positive experiences with respect to the learning devices. The ought to encourage the COVID-19 conditions may have guaranteed the effective execution of the innovations, subsequently improving understudy scholarly execution (Adnan, 2020).

CONCLUSION

The around the world COVID-19 widespread has postured serious challenges for social orders over the globe. One of these rising challenges was the requirements for fast digitalization of all life spaces counting instruction. This improvement carries both threats

and openings for execution evaluation in higher instruction. The wide usage and thorough testing of strategies that moderate cheating through higher responsibility or complexity as well as the dialog of scholastic standards which will ruin the execution of modern and imaginative modes of examination (e.g., open-book and collaborative exams) is in this manner a vital assignment for instructive investigate and hone is needed. Besides, the rate of cheating in exams amid this time depended on the examination mode, with online exams being more inclined to the utilization of unpermitted help at that point on-site exams. An upside to these discoveries is that they challenge higher institutions of education teach to discover answers on challenges that were as of now rising and simply quickened by the widespread. Online testing will likely be a marvel of remaining and expanding pertinence. This improvement carries both threats and openings for execution evaluation in higher instruction. The coming of the widespread on a very basic level changed the way HEIs provide instruction over the globe. In arrange to manage with confinements on person-to-person intelligent, HEIs have quickened their move to online learning with significant results for both understudies and workforce. This move has been encouraged by the integration of online innovations such as Zoom and Moodle into course conveyance frameworks which have in turn actuates changes to conventional F2F educational hones to suit e-learning for diverse information spaces. This survey has distinguished some imperative challenges to viable online move: coordination synchronous and offbeat devices into consistent online conveyance, overcoming obstructions to innovation get to, moving forward online competencies for learners and workforce, overcoming scholarly untrustworthiness issues in online evaluation, and security and secrecy. This study moreover recognized methodologies that may be joined into a best hone system for online instruction. To begin with, organization bolster ought to be unmistakable and multifaceted with a specific centre on online learning materials advancement and innovation back for staff and understudies. Moment, in arrange to mitigate the impacts of any future emergencies, mixed learning ought to be grasped as an obligatory component of face to face instruction in a post-COVID world. Third, preparing in instructive advances and their successful utilize ought to be accessible to staff and understudies who require it.

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